

CREATION OF NORMATIVE AND LEGAL BASES OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract : This in the article Uzbekistan in the Republic higher education system formation and in development regulatory and legal of the foundations importance analysis done Independence years acceptance done laws and normative documents , they education system modernization in doing place and higher education quality to increase directed reforms studied .

Key words : high education , regulatory and legal foundations , reforms , education quality , modernization .

Introduction . Uzbekistan to independence from achieving then education field of the state main priority from directions to one became In particular , high education system of the country socio-economic and scientific and technical development service doer personnel preparation goal did Our country higher education in the system done being increased reforms efficiency provide qualified education to managers directly depends in Uzbekistan next in years done being increased wide scope of reforms content , first First , our economy all networks fast pictures with consistent from development consists of This task successful done in increasing networks for deep knowledge and practical to skills have potential young personnel preparation separately place occupies This the target is a person capital upgrade Uzbekistan development the most important , integral part of the strategy from the parts is one It's on the way higher education system each bilaterally develop it qualified and practical to the experience have has been passionate specialists with to provide directed wide scope affairs done is increasing . Practice being increased systematic measures as a result higher education of institutions material and technical base , legal-normative , methodological supply step by step getting stronger is going

Main part. The last in years in Uzbekistan foreign of countries higher study with in cooperation their branches and joint education institutions organize being done attention deserves This activity more acceleration need This is the case local higher study of their countries they are with to competition and personnel in preparation quality level to increase take will come

Uzbekistan Republic of In Article 41 of the 1992 Constitution , " Each who knowledge get to the right has " note done In this country education system development constitutional basis created That's it with together , accepted in 1997 done " Education about". the law and Personnel preparation national program education a radical turn in the field made This program higher education modernization make , personnel preparation quality international to standards adaptation and modern education infrastructure to create mean caught President in 2017 Shaukat Mirziyoyev initiative with acceptance done Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 Republic development five priority direction according to Actions strategy within

education system , including higher education quality to increase separately attention was directed . This period the following main normative documents acceptance done :

High education system development according to President decisions : high study countries number reproduction , new direction and of faculties opening

International of universities to Uzbekistan attraction Education : Polytechnic of Turin University , Inha University , and others

Admission in 2018 done " Innovative development about". the law education system scientific research potential to increase directed was This is a document higher education institutions with science integration strengthened and international grants attraction to do opportunities expanded . Admission in 2020 done " Education quality control to do agency" . organize reach about decision of education quality indicators evaluation system current did This decision within education programs international to standards according to updated and higher study of their countries autonomy increased

That's it in a sense state education organizations development for how much conditions if it creates , non-state education organize organizations reach and activity conduct for from him less didn't happen organizational , legal conditions create , material help to show a must Therefore it is private education organizations wide privilege and preferences present reached , this field is being developed . New in Uzbekistan higher education system fundamentally reform is being done . Including private higher study countries opening , foreign universities branches the number increasing , distant university in the regions as well branches organize in progress , 41 state higher study to their countries academic and financial independence given Also to universities acceptance last six 5 times per year increased , students number to 1 million enough Coverage and from 9 percent to 38 percent increased An example for , in 2016 77 in Uzbekistan university has been if so , now their the number is 210 organize is doing The last one six in grants 2 times the number increased to 40 thousand enough From that , a master's degree for - 5 times increased . High education system international standards based on activity conduct - him administrative from management pulling educational and scientific research process organize in reaching academic to freedom have to be requirement is enough That's it relationship with new edited Our constitution Article 51 of the draft " High education organizations to the law according to academic freedom , self himself management , research transfer and teaching freedom to the right he said the rule is being determined .

Conclusion. Uzbekistan in the Republic higher education system development according to acceptance done regulatory and legal documents education quality to increase and competitive personnel to prepare directed . Reforms as a result higher education system international to standards adapted , this while Uzbekistan in the global arena competitiveness in increasing important importance occupation did Uzbekistan Republic President of October 8 , 2019 Decree with approved " Uzbekistan Republic higher education system until 2030 development concept". according to of our country higher education in the field reforms done increase , of people worldview change , mature and time on demand answer giving expert personnel preparation of life himself requirement is doing In this mature expert personnel training , education and education to give system reforms requirements with closely connected to be important importance occupation is enough Today in the day higher education in institutions study processes planning and organize in : Uzbekistan Republic of Constitution , " Education about". Law , Uzbekistan Republic President higher to education

about decrees and decisions , Ministers Court decisions as well High education science and innovation of the ministry commands such as normative documents in practice is being used . But that's it to the day until education and education processes organize doer subjects by this documents in practice their use theoretical and practical aspects almost not studied . These are the cases higher education in institutions applied higher of education regulatory and legal the basics each bilaterally theoretical and practical in terms of learning and analysis to reach from relevance proof gives

References:

- 1.Khakimova Khulkar Khamitovna IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT STRATEGY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN // SAI. Special Issue 7 transaction : 24.11.2024).
- 2.Khojamberdiyev Rozimammed It's a boy PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING THE LEGAL BASIS OF OLY EDUCATION // Interpretation and studies scientific and methodical magazine . 2022. #10. URL : https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/prospects_for_improving_the_legal_basis_of_education (data obr ashcheniya : 24.11.2024) .
- 3.<https://lib.bimm.uz/items/download/11542>
- 4.Uzbekistan Republic higher education system development until 2030 concept confirmation about , Uzbekistan Republic President Decree No. PF-5847 dated 08.10.2019 , <https://lex.uz/docs/-4545884> .
- 5.Regulatory and legal documents about , Uzbekistan Republic of Law , O'RQ-682 dated 20.04.2021, <https://lex.uz/docs/-5378966>.

